

Persistent organic pollutants in selected Icelandic food matrices: a multimatrix screening approach

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the presence of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in locally sourced Icelandic foods, covering wild and farmed fish, fish-derived products, terrestrial meats, puffin meat, and berries. The highest contaminant levels were measured in shark and fish liver, with PBDEs and pesticides reaching 97 ng/g ww and 13755 ng/g ww, respectively. Notable variations in the relative contaminant distribution were observed among sample types. Although most concentrations measured were below current EU Maximum Residue Levels, shark and Atlantic puffin exceeded regulatory limits for certain contaminants, suggesting that these products may not be suitable for human consumption unless appropriate safety controls are applied. Higher concentrations of lipophilic compounds (PBDEs, organochlorine pesticides, PCBs, PCDD/Fs) were observed in fatty matrices such as liver, consistent with their well-established bioaccumulative behavior. These findings highlight the need for monitoring high-risk food products and broadening contaminant surveillance to non-marine local foods, which are often overlooked despite their dietary importance for Arctic populations.

1. Introduction

Despite the increasing efforts by both the authorities and the scientific community to ensure consumer protection worldwide, the Arctic populations are still exposed to high contaminant levels through diet. The traditional Arctic diet relies heavily on marine products including fish and fish-derived products, which have been repeatedly identified as the food groups containing the highest organic contaminant levels (Abass et al., 2022; ANSES, 2011; Arrebola et al., 2018). Fish fillet, fish liver, fish oil, marine mammals, or crustaceans, among other marine food items, can bioaccumulate high levels of persistent organic pollutants (POPs), particularly the most lipophilic compounds such as organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), polybrominated biphenyls (PBBs), polychlorinated dibenzodioxins and furans (PCDD/Fs), and polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs).

As a result of recent regulations and restrictions in the production, use, and release of most of these substances worldwide, the POP levels in aquatic environments has undergone a steady decrease over the past decades (Lakhmanov et al., 2020; Nøstbakken et al., 2015; Sturludottir

et al., 2014). However, this decline appears to be slowing down, and recent studies have reported stable or even increasing concentrations for certain compounds (Boitsov et al., 2019, 2024), which suggests that environmental persistence and ongoing secondary emissions may sustain high background contamination levels (Karl et al., 2016). The potential exposure risk linked to fish consumption has been highlighted in the past regarding multiple contaminant families such as PCBs and PCDD/Fs (Struciński et al., 2013), per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) (Kowalczyk et al., 2020), among others, and can even result in the prohibition of sale of certain fish species caught in Arctic regions for human consumption, as occurred in Denmark for salmon and herring from the Baltic Sea in 2011 (Ministeriet for Fødevarer Landbrug og Fiskeri (Denmark), 2011). Other initiatives aimed at ensuring consumer protection such as the Arctic Char Distribution Project adopt a different approach by promoting the substitution of highly contaminated food products with alternatives that have lower contaminant levels (Gautier et al., 2016). Despite these efforts, many food products known to contain extremely high levels of contaminants are still consumed, particularly those derived from long-lived species or organisms at the top of the food

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chain, where bioaccumulation and biomagnification effects become more pronounced (Corsolini et al., 2016; Molde et al., 2013; Rawn et al., 2009; Remili et al., 2023). An example of this is the traditional consumption of fermented or cured shark meat, a traditional Icelandic dish which is mostly consumed around a mid-winter festival period called þorri. Fermented Greenland shark is no longer an important source of protein and energy for the Icelandic population throughout the year, and it is mainly consumed as a seasonal delicacy during the festival (late January to February) and by tourists (S. Jensen et al., 2023; Skåra et al., 2015). However, the raw material is either sourced from local fishermen catching a few individuals per season, or obtained as by-catch from commercial trawler fisheries, and therefore, contaminant monitoring of this food item is limited or not systematically conducted. This leads to its occasional consumption being associated with higher exposure to certain contaminants such as mercury (Dufþaksdóttir et al., 2023).

This well-established link between fish consumption and contaminant exposure has, however, led most contaminant monitoring studies to focus almost exclusively on marine organisms, while largely overlooking other local food items such as meat, dairy products, fruits, or vegetables that are also an important part of Icelandic diets. Their underrepresentation in both national monitoring programs and the scientific literature prevents a comprehensive assessment of actual dietary exposure of the Icelandic populations (Nalbandyan-Schwarz et al., 2024). In this sense, the consumption of berries, mushrooms, and meat has been recently correlated to blood levels of certain OCPs and PCBs in one study set in the Finnish Lapland that considered multiple categories of locally sourced food items beyond fish and seafood (Abass et al., 2022).

Arctic populations are not a homogeneous group in terms of dietary patterns, and important differences exist across regions. In Greenland, Canada, Alaska and parts of North-East Russia, traditional diets include substantial consumption of marine mammals and wild game, which have been consistently associated with elevated POP exposure (Deutch et al., 2007). In contrast, the consumption of these items is much lower in other parts of the Arctic and sub-Arctic regions, including the Nordic countries (Robards & Reeves, 2011). Specifically, the Icelandic diet is generally characterized by a high consumption of fish and sheep meat, with very limited intake of marine mammals. Recent national dietary surveys further indicate comparatively low consumption of fruits, vegetables, and red meat in Iceland within the Nordic region (Nordic Council of Ministers, 2024). These distinctions suggest that dietary patterns and contaminant exposure observed in a specific Arctic communities cannot be directly extrapolated to others, and region-specific assessments are therefore essential for the accurate evaluation of dietary habits.

This study aims to provide an initial exploration of the presence of persistent organic pollutants (PFAS, PBDEs, PBBs, OCPs, PCBs, and PCDD/Fs) in locally sourced Icelandic food items, based on a matrix selection covering a wide range of food origins and categories (terrestrial, marine, animal, and plant-based). The matrix selection prioritized matrix diversity as a means of encompassing, within a limited set of samples, some of the most relevant local food items for consumer exposure assessment in Iceland. Although a substantial proportion of food consumed in Iceland is imported due to the country's climatic constraints, locally sourced foods remain an important component of traditional dietary habits and potential contaminant exposure. Hence, the items analyzed in the present work are either commonly consumed by the Icelandic population, such as lamb meat, or represent a higher potential risk due to the contaminant levels expected, such as shark. Particular emphasis was placed on fish and fish-derived products, as they simultaneously meet both criteria. The sample selection was also intended as a pilot study to inform and support a forthcoming large-scale monitoring aimed at characterizing dietary exposure to POPs across a broader range of food items and Arctic regions.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Food commodities

The samples used in this study were collected in Iceland during the autumn of 2024 and encompassed 11 fish samples (wild salmon, farmed salmon, wild char, farmed char, cod fillet, plaice fillet, shark meat, cod liver, haddock liver, cod liver oil, mackerel crude oil), two terrestrial meat samples (lamb, mutton), one seabird sample (puffin meat, representing a pelagic species that breeds on land but feeds predominantly within marine food webs), and two berry samples (blueberries, crowberries). The animal tissue samples were either acquired at retail level, from production facilities or directly from farmers, fishermen and anglers. Cod, haddock, and plaice samples were collected in the fjord of Eyjafjörður, a fjord that lies in the north of Iceland with several settlements (including Akureyri, the fourth largest town of Iceland) and a combined population of approximately 25000 people. In this area, it is common that individuals have small vessels and fish locally for own consumption. White fish tissues and liver samples of these species were collected from such local fishermen. Similarly, the shark meat sample used in this study was obtained from a Greenland shark caught as bycatch in the waters of the west peninsula and after processing at a facility approved by the Competent Authority in accordance with EU food legislation in Eyjafjörður (European Commission, 2004, 2017). Wild Arctic char and wild salmon samples were collected directly by anglers, the Arctic char from a river remotely located in the north of Iceland, and the salmon in a river in the south-west. A significant percentage of the Icelandic population include in their daily diet a sip of processed cod liver oil as a health supplement. There are several producers on the local market, and the cod liver oil employed in the present study belonged to the most traditional type and brand found at retail level in Iceland. The mackerel crude oil sample was acquired from one of the fishmeal processing facilities located in the east coast of Iceland, which harvest pelagic species such as herring, blue whiting, capelin and mackerel both for human consumption and the feed industry. In Iceland, there has been in recent years a rapid built up of sea cage salmon farming and also a growing investment in land-based operations for both salmon and Arctic char. Samples of farmed salmon and char were acquired at retail level from local producers. Meat samples from lamb, mutton and puffin were sourced in the municipality of Norðurþing in the north-east of Iceland. Finally, private wild harvesting and consumption of crow- and blueberries is very common practice every autumn in Iceland, but such products are not available at retail level. The berry samples used in this study were collected in the field in the inland of Eyjafjörður in the north-east of Iceland.

2.2. Extraction and analysis: PFAS

Sample preparation for PFAS analysis was performed according to a previously described methodology (Díaz-Galiano et al., 2023). Briefly, isotopically-labelled internal standards ($^{13}\text{C}_3$ -GenX, $^2\text{H}_5$ -N-EtFOSAA, $^2\text{H}_3$ -N-MeFOSAA, $^{13}\text{C}_4$ -PFBA, $^{13}\text{C}_3$ -PFBS, $^{13}\text{C}_2$ -PFDA, $^{13}\text{C}_2$ -PFDoDA, $^{13}\text{C}_4$ -PFHpA, $^{13}\text{C}_2$ -PFHxA, $^{18}\text{O}_2$ -PFHxS, $^{13}\text{C}_5$ -PFNA, $^{13}\text{C}_4$ -PFOA, $^{13}\text{C}_4$ -PFOS, $^{13}\text{C}_3$ -PFPeA, $^{13}\text{C}_2$ -PFTeDA, $^{13}\text{C}_2$ -PFUnDA) were added to 1 g of freeze-dried sample, followed by 15 mL of a KOH solution in MeOH (0.01 M) and vortex agitation. After 16 h at room temperature, a 5-mL aliquot of the supernatant was evaporated to 1 mL, and 4 mL of water were added. Sample purification was performed in two solid-phase extraction (SPE) steps. Firstly, CHROMABOND® PFAS SPE cartridges were pre-conditioned using 10 mL of a MeOH/NH₄OH solution (99.5:0.5, v/v), 10 mL of MeOH, and 10 mL of ultrapure water; the sample was then loaded into the cartridges, which were rinsed with 5 mL of an aqueous solution of ammonium acetate (20 mM) and 5 mL of MeOH. Samples were then eluted with 7.5 mL of a MeOH/NH₄OH solution (99.5:0.5, v/v). In the second step, the samples were re-evaporated to 1 mL, loaded into ENVICARB™ SPE cartridges

pre-conditioned with 10 mL of MeOH, and eluted with 6 mL of a solution of MeOH and glacial acetic acid (80:1, v/v). Finally, each extract was evaporated to dryness and reconstituted with 50 μ L of MeOH (containing $^{13}\text{C}_8$ -PFOS as the recovery standard) and 80 μ L of ultrapure water.

The analysis of PFAS was performed using an Agilent 1290 Infinity II coupled with an Agilent 6495C LC-TQ (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA). The injection volume was 4 μ L, and the chromatographic separation was carried out with a Hypersil Gold column (100 \times 2.1 mm, particle size 1.9 μ m) at a flow of 0.6 mL/min and 50 $^\circ\text{C}$. The system employed 0.02 M of ammonium acetate in milliQ water (mobile phase A) and methanol (mobile phase B) with the following gradient: 30 % B held for 0.5 min, followed by linear gradients up to 67.5 % B at 3 min, up to 69.5 % (5 min), up to 73.5 % (7 min), and finally 95 % (7.5 min, held for 1 min). An equilibration step was then performed by returning to 30% B for 2.5 min. The electrospray ion source (negative mode) employed nitrogen as the nebulizer gas at 12 L/min, 30 psi for the nebulizer pressure, and 400 $^\circ\text{C}$ for the sheath gas temperature. The MS used nitrogen as the collision gas (99.999% purity) and 2000 V for the capillary voltage. All compounds were analyzed in MRM mode. The following PFAS were analyzed: PFBS, PFPeS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS, PFNS, PFDS, PFUnDS, PFDoDS, PFTrDS, PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDoDA, PFTrDA, PFTeDA, N-MeFOSAA, N-EtFOSAA, GenX, DONA, F53B major, F53B minor.

Following EU Regulation 2023/915 for PFAS analysis in food samples, the PFAS concentrations were calculated and reported as lower bound –i.e., all the values below the limit of quantification (LOQ) were considered as zero– (European Commission, 2023).

2.3. Extraction and analysis: organochlorine pesticides

Freeze-dried samples (1 g) were spiked with isotopically-labelled standards corresponding to each target analyte included in the analytical scope, and 20 mL of a mixture hexane/acetone (1:1, v/v) were added. The extraction of organochlorine pesticides was performed using a microwave-assisted methodology (800 W, 100 $^\circ\text{C}$, 15 min), following solvent evaporation to 500 μ L. Hexane (5 mL) and acetonitrile (5 mL) were added, and the extracts were vortexed and centrifuged before separating the two phases. Then, a liquid-liquid partitioning step was then performed: 5 mL of acetonitrile were added to the hexane phase, and 5 mL of hexane were added to the acetonitrile phase, followed by vortex and centrifugation. Then, the two new phases were separated and combined with their respective original solvent phases, resulting in two combined fractions: one in hexane and one in acetonitrile.

The hexane fraction, containing pesticide residues stable on acid silica, was purified by a multilayer column containing Florisil, sodium sulfate, neuter silica gel, and acid silica gel. Extracts were loaded onto the columns (pre-conditioned with dichloromethane followed by hexane) and eluted with a mixture of hexane/dichloromethane 1:1.

The acetonitrile fraction, containing pesticide residues labile on acid silica, was subjected to further clean-up through two consecutive SPE steps. The first SPE was performed on cartridges containing neuter silica and sodium sulfate, which were pre-conditioned with dichloromethane and hexane. Samples were loaded onto these cartridges and eluted with a mixture hexane/acetone (9:1, v/v). After evaporation to a final volume of approximately 200 μ L, the extracts were subjected to a second SPE clean-up using cartridges containing Florisil and additional sodium sulfate, pre-conditioned in the same manner. Elution was carried out with the same hexane/acetone mixture.

The purified extracts were then combined and evaporated to dryness before adding 50 μ L of toluene as the injection solvent and ^{13}C -PCB-111 as the recovery standard. Samples were separated using an Agilent 7890 GC equipped with a HT8-PCB Trajan column (60 m \times 0.25 mm \times 0.25 μ m). The injector was kept at 250 $^\circ\text{C}$ in splitless mode, with an injection volume of 2 μ L. The temperature ramp in the chromatographic oven began at 120 $^\circ\text{C}$ (hold 1 min), then it was increased up to 180 $^\circ\text{C}$ (20 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, hold for 1 min), up to 290 $^\circ\text{C}$ (5 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$), and finally to 300 $^\circ\text{C}$

(20 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, hold for 1.5 min). The detection of compounds was performed using an Agilent 7010 Triple Quadrupole with electronic impact ionization and a source temperature of 250 $^\circ\text{C}$. The residues analyzed in the present study included PeCB, HCB, α -HCH, β -HCH, γ -HCH, δ -HCH, heptachlor, heptachlor endo-epoxide, heptachlor exo-epoxide, aldrin, endrin, dieldrin, cis-chlordane, trans-chlordane, oxychlordane, o,p'-DDE, p,p'-DDE, o,p'-DDD, p,p'-DDD, o,p'-DDT, p,p'-DDT, cis-nonachlor, trans-nonachlor, α -endosulfan, β -endosulfan, endosulfan sulfate, mirex. The concentrations of the detected pesticides were calculated and reported as lower bound, as described by previous authors (Kesse-Guyot et al., 2023).

2.4. Extraction and analysis: PBDEs, PBBs, PCBs, and PCDD/Fs

Isotopically-labelled internal standards of all target contaminants included in the analytical scope were added to the freeze-dried samples (3 g) prior to extraction. Pressurized liquid extraction (PLE) was carried out using a Speed Extractor E-914 (Büchi) with a toluene/acetone mixture (70:30, v/v) under conditions of 120 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 100 bar, applying three extraction cycles. The resulting extracts were evaporated to dryness, reconstituted with 5 mL of hexane and 400 μ L of ethyl acetate, and placed in an ultrasonic bath for 1 min to ensure complete dissolution of the analytes. Sample purification was performed automatically using a GO-EHT system (Miura). The extracts first passed through a two-step column set consisting of a silver nitrate/silica gel column followed by an acid silica gel column, both using hexane as the carrier solvent. After this initial purification, analytes were separated based on their chemical nature: dioxins, furans, and coplanar PCBs were retained on a carbon column, while non-coplanar PCBs, PBBs, and PBDEs were retained on an aluminum oxide column. All analytes were eluted with toluene at high temperature, and the extracts were then evaporated to dryness and reconstituted in the injection solvent. Recovery standards (^{13}C -PCB-111, ^{13}C -BDE-79, ^{13}C -BDE-138, ^{13}C -1,2,3,4-TCDD) were also added to the samples.

An Agilent 7890A Gas Chromatograph coupled to a Jéol – HRMS 800 D was employed for the analysis. Chromatographic separation employed helium as the carrier gas (1 mL/min). The injection was performed in splitless mode (2 μ L). The injector was kept at a constant temperature of 280 $^\circ\text{C}$, and the initial oven temperature was set at 120 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 min. Electronic impact ionization was performed, with a source temperature of 280 $^\circ\text{C}$.

For PBDEs and PBBs, the temperature was raised up to 215 $^\circ\text{C}$ (10 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$), then to 270 $^\circ\text{C}$ (3 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$), and finally to 310 $^\circ\text{C}$ (10 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, hold for 4 min), using a DB5MS column (30 m \times 0.25 mm \times 0.25 μ m). The following congeners were analyzed: BDE 28, 47, 49, 66, 85, 99, 100, 153, 154, 183, 196, 197, 206, 207, 209; PBB 52, 101, 153. For BDE 209, an Rtx1614 column (15m \times 0.25 mm \times 0.10 μ m) was used; the injector was kept at 295 $^\circ\text{C}$ in splitless mode, with an injection volume of 2 μ L, and the temperature ramp in the chromatographic oven began at 130 $^\circ\text{C}$ (hold 4 min), then it was increased up to 335 $^\circ\text{C}$ (40 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, hold for 1 min).

For PCBs, an HT8-PCB Trajan column (60 m \times 0.25 mm \times 0.25 μ m) was used to separate the compounds, with a first temperature ramp up to 200 $^\circ\text{C}$ (20 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$), then to 260 $^\circ\text{C}$ (3 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$), and finally to 330 $^\circ\text{C}$ (30 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, hold for 2.5 min). Congeners #77, 81, 126, 169, 105, 114, 118, 123, 156, 157, 167, 189, 28, 52, 101, 138, 153, and 180 were analyzed.

For PCDD/Fs, the temperature was increased to 200 $^\circ\text{C}$ (50 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$), then to 300 $^\circ\text{C}$ (4 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$), and finally to 325 $^\circ\text{C}$ (40 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, hold for 3 min) on a DB5MS column (60 m \times 0.25 mm \times 0.25 μ m). The following compounds were analyzed: 2,3,7,8-TCDD; 1,2,3,7,8-PeCDD; 1,2,3,4,7,8-HxCDD; 1,2,3,6,7,8-HxCDD; 1,2,3,7,8,9-HxCDD; 1,2,3,4,6,7,8-HpCDD; OCDD; 2,3,7,8-TCDF; 1,2,3,7,8-PeCDF; 2,3,4,7,8-PeCDF; 1,2,3,4,7,8-HxCDF; 1,2,3,6,7,8-HxCDF; 1,2,3,7,8,9-HxCDF; 2,3,4,6,7,8-HxCDF; 1,2,3,4,6,7,8-HpCDF; 1,2,3,4,7,8,9-HpCDF; OCDF.

Following EU Regulation 2023/915 for PCBs and PCDD/Fs, analysis

in food samples, the concentrations of these contaminant families were calculated and reported as upper bound –i.e., all the values below the limit of quantification were considered as equal to the LOQ– (European Commission, 2023).

2.5. QA/QC

To ensure the quality of the analysis, besides the use of appropriate internal standards in each sample, labelled external standards were systematically added at the end of each analytical process in order to determine recoveries, which were in all cases within the 60–140 % range. Further, a continuous monitoring of the analytical procedure was implemented through procedural blanks. Reproducibility was assessed using quality control samples (QC) of fish and meat naturally contaminated with PFAS, OCPs, PBDEs, PCBs, and PCDD/Fs, which are regularly characterized over several years. The accuracy of the analytical methods was further ensured by regular participation of the laboratory to proficiency tests, such as those organized by the European Reference Laboratory (EURL) for POPs. The measured concentrations of PFAS, OCPs, PBDEs, PBBs, PCBs and PCDD/Fs congeners were expressed on a wet weight (ww) basis. The LOQ was set as the concentration corresponding to a signal to noise exceeding 3 and was calculated individually for each molecule in each tested food sample. All methods were performed according to an ISO standard 17025-accredited system.

For PFAS analysis, special precautions were taken to minimize background contamination and analyte loss. Materials containing glass or fluoropolymers were avoided throughout the analytical workflow, and polypropylene or high-density polyethylene labware was used whenever possible. Ultrapure water was routinely checked for PFAS contamination, and procedural blanks were systematically analyzed to monitor potential laboratory background contributions. No significant PFAS contamination was detected in blank samples.

3. Results and discussion

All compounds included in the analytical scope of this study are included in the Stockholm Convention for POPs or belong to chemical families for which selected congeners are regulated under the Convention (such as PFAS, where not only those listed as POPs are herein analyzed, but also additional congeners). Some of the target compounds –i.e., OCPs, PCBs, PCDD/Fs– are considered as “legacy” contaminants and were already included in the initial version of the Stockholm Convention, while others –PFAS and PBDEs– have emerged in the past decades as contaminants of concern due to their environmental ubiquity and persistence. In the following sections, the results are presented and discussed by chemical family, providing a comparative overview of their occurrence and distribution across the analyzed food matrices. The complete dataset can be found in the Supplementary Material.

3.1. Emerging contaminants: PFAS

A total of 21 out of the 27 PFAS included in the analytical scope were detected across the food samples analyzed, with substantial variability in both the number of compounds and the concentration levels depending on the matrix (Fig. 1a). Unlike legacy POPs such as PBDEs, PCBs, and OCPs, PFAS are not lipophilic compounds but are generally highly water-soluble and protein-affine substances, which results in distinct environmental behavior and tissue distribution patterns. The highest total PFAS concentrations were measured in haddock liver (2.68 ng/g ww), followed by puffin (1.42 ng/g ww) and shark (1.26 ng/g ww). The remarkably high contaminant levels detected in puffin might be attributed to its predominantly piscivorous diet, which results in a higher exposure to organic contaminants that reach the Arctic regions through long-range oceanic transport.

Conversely, no PFAS residues were detected in any of the oil samples. This result is noteworthy considering that both oils were derived from fish tissues –primarily livers– that exhibited high PFAS concentrations. Two factors may partly account for this observation: matrix complexity and contaminant partitioning behavior. Fish oils, rich in co-extracted lipophilic compounds, may have introduced background noise and signal suppression effects, thereby elevating the effective limits of detection (LOQs). Notably, the LOQs for several long-chain perfluoroalkyl carboxylic acids (e.g., PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDoDA, PFTrDA), which were among the predominant PFAS in most marine matrices, were higher in oil samples than in the remaining food types (Supplementary Material). In some cases, these LOQs even exceeded concentration levels detected in other samples. This suggests that low levels of these compounds, if present in oils, may have remained undetected due to the analytical challenges inherent to this type of matrix (i.e., signal suppression). In addition, PFAS are known to bind preferentially to proteins in blood, liver, and muscle tissues rather than accumulate in lipid fractions, which is consistent with their absence in oil matrices. However, certain PFAS may exhibit more complex distribution patterns, and the partitioning behavior cannot be fully ascertained within the scope of this study. No previous studies addressing the occurrence of PFAS in fish liver oil from Arctic species could be retrieved for comparison; however, one study analyzing commercially available fish oil of unspecified origin also reported non-detectable levels of these contaminants (Suominen et al., 2011), and no clear associations have been observed between fish oil supplement consumption and PFAS levels in human blood (Onteeru et al., 2022).

Marine samples and puffin contained on average nine different PFAS, with haddock liver showing the highest chemical diversity: 16 congeners were detected in this matrix. In contrast, terrestrial samples such as meat and berries contained only two or one PFAS, respectively. Although some fish, such as farmed salmon or char, showed relatively low total PFAS concentrations (<0.7 ng/g ww), they still contained a

Fig. 1. Total concentration, total number of contaminants (a), and contaminant sample profiles (b) of PFAS in the analyzed samples. PFAS for which an EU-MRL in food commodities has been set are marked with an asterisk.

broader diversity of compounds compared to sheep and berry samples. This greater chemical diversity, even in samples with modest concentrations, suggests a widespread distribution of PFAS in marine ecosystems. Although Arctic terrestrial environments are also impacted by these contaminants (Dai et al., 2025), the higher diversity and concentrations observed in marine samples are consistent with literature describing stronger biomagnification in marine food webs compared to terrestrial systems (Müller et al., 2011), as well as generally higher PFAS burdens in marine biota and seafood (Dimitrakopoulou et al., 2024). Similarly, studies in Arctic fauna have linked elevated PFAS levels to diets with a higher marine component (Herzke et al., 2023; Tartu et al., 2017). In addition, long-range oceanic transport has been identified as an important pathway for PFAS delivery to the Arctic (Armitage et al., 2006), further supporting the impact of these contaminants in marine ecosystems. However, the scarcity of previous studies or reports analyzing the presence of PFAS in terrestrial food samples from the Arctic prevents any direct comparison and highlights the need for further research in this area.

As previously described, haddock liver contained the highest PFAS levels, accounting for three times more than those found in cod liver. Despite the lack of previous studies describing the analysis of PFAS in haddock liver from the Arctic, cod liver has been analyzed in at least four separate studies, which provides a reference for PFAS occurrence in this type of matrix. In 2014, Jörundsdóttir et al. investigated the presence of nine PFAS in pooled cod liver samples (among other organs and fish species) collected in Icelandic waters, detecting only PFOS at levels between 0.35 and 0.62 ng/g ww (Jörundsdóttir et al., 2014). PFOS was not detected in cod liver in the present study; instead, seven other PFAS were identified, most of them at comparatively lower concentrations. The remaining studies also found PFOS and other congeners in cod liver samples from Norway (Dale et al., 2019; Valdersnes et al., 2017) and the Barents Sea (Kowalczyk et al., 2020), usually at higher levels than those found in the present study.

The total PFAS load in wild salmon was 8.9 times higher than in farmed salmon (0.551 ng/g ww compared to 0.062 ng/g ww, respectively), and 2.5 times higher in wild compared to farmed char (0.088 ng/g ww compared to 0.036). These results are in accordance with previous literature on organic contaminant levels in wild versus farmed fish from the Arctic (I. J. Jensen et al., 2020; Lundebye et al., 2017); however, those studies did not include PFAS, and, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first time PFAS concentrations have been directly compared between wild and farmed fish from Arctic regions.

Regarding compound-specific trends, PFOS and long-chain perfluorocarboxylic acids (PFOA to PFTrDA) were in general the most prevalent compounds across samples, both in terms of concentrations and ubiquity. PFOS dominated the PFAS profile of six samples, including salmon (farmed and wild), farmed char, plaice, lamb, and mutton (Fig. 1b), while other PFAS occasionally reached higher concentrations in specific samples. Notably, PFBA was detected in only three samples, but its levels were unusually high (up to 0.51 ng/g ww in cod liver). This highlights the importance of considering both concentration and frequency of detection when assessing the environmental and toxicological relevance of individual PFAS.

The European Commission sets MRLs for the lower bound concentration of PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS, and their summed levels in certain food commodities of animal origin (European Commission, 2023). Among the samples analyzed within the present study, this regulation is applicable to all fish muscle and meat samples, which were in all cases well below the corresponding MRLs. The shark sample, which showed the highest PFAS concentrations among eligible matrices, showed still approximately 10 times lower levels than the regulatory threshold for the summed congeners (0.21 ng/g ww compared to 2 ng/g ww, respectively).

3.2. Legacy POPs: organochlorine pesticides

A total of 27 pesticide residues were included in the analytical scope of this study, some of which are structurally related (including isomers and known degradation products). Shark meat displayed unusually high levels of 13755 ng/g ww, between two and five orders of magnitude higher than the remaining samples (Fig. 2a). Considering the long lifespan of Greenlandic sharks, estimated between 250 and 500 years, and the high position they occupy in the trophic chain, this finding illustrates the potential for OCPs and other lipophilic POPs to bioaccumulate and biomagnify in animal tissues, as previously described (Corsolini et al., 2016; Molde et al., 2013). The second highest levels were identified in cod liver (73 ng/g ww), and these were remarkably higher than those found in haddock liver (21 ng/g ww), similarly to the findings of previous works comparing both types of matrix (Boitsov et al., 2019, 2024). Notably, in this case, no pesticide residues were detected in cod liver oil; this commercially available item is extensively purified by the manufacturer during production and processing, which may have influenced the absence of detectable pesticide residues. The reduced contaminant load in processed fish oils in comparison to fish liver was already described in samples from Iceland and the Baltic Sea (Falandysz, Smith, Panton, & Fernandes, 2019). In contrast, crude mackerel oil was not subjected to any preprocessing steps by the manufacturer and displayed a high summed concentration of 49.32 ng/g ww. Despite the lack of scientific literature on the analysis of pesticides in raw fish oil samples, OCP residues -dominated by DDT-were detected in all fish oil supplements analyzed in Canadian fish oil supplement by Rawn et al. (Rawn et al., 2009).

Conversely to the PFAS findings, there was no clear differences between wild and farmed fish samples, and similar levels and sample profiles of pesticides and other legacy POPs were observed for salmon and char regardless of production method. This was observed despite the regulated composition and monitoring of aquaculture feed, suggesting that, for these compound groups, production method did not markedly influence the contamination patterns.

Cod and plaice fillets contained the lowest OCP levels among the marine samples, with total concentrations similar to those found in lamb and mutton. In contrast, puffin once again showed high contaminant levels more closely aligned with marine species. Conversely to the case of PFAS, the number of OCPs detected in meat samples was similar to that found in marine samples (an average of 18 out of the 27 compounds analyzed), while berries were the samples with the lowest pesticide diversity: only five and six pesticide residues were identified in crowberries and blueberries, respectively. The total pesticide load in these two vegetable matrices (down to 0.08 ng/g ww) was, also, the lowest. The levels herein reported for wild berries from the Arctic are in accordance with those recently reported by previous works (Abass et al., 2022; Nalbandyan-Schwarz et al., 2024).

As displayed in Fig. 2b, the OCP sample profiles were dominated by DDT derivatives for most samples. The sum of p,p'- and o,p'- isomers for DDD, DDE, and DDT accounted for a minimum of 22 % (haddock liver sample) and up to 80 % (shark) of the total OCP load, with p,p'-DDE being the major contributor. The prevalence of p,p'-DDE over the remaining DDT derivatives has been previously reported for food samples from the Arctic regions (Corsolini et al., 2006; Dale et al., 2019). The reason for this is likely related to the higher potential for bioaccumulation and longer half-life of DDE in animal fat tissues (Hunnego & Harrison, 1971), and the selective metabolization of DDT into p, p-DDE in living organisms (French & Jefferies, 1969). The predominance of p,p'-DDE was further reflected in the (DDE + DDD)/DDT and DDE/DDT ratios, which were consistently above the threshold set by multiple studies as indicators of historical rather than recent DDT contamination (Alam et al., 2014; Cotronei et al., 2018; Spataro et al., 2021).

Following DDT, other important contributors were HCB and non-achlor, which accounted for up to 42.1 and 22.2 % of the sample

Fig. 2. Total concentration (a, c, e, g) and contaminant sample profiles (b,d, f, h) of legacy contaminants.

profiles, respectively. HCB has been recently reported as the only OCP residue whose concentrations in fish samples from the Arctic have not decreased, but increased in the past decades (Boitsov et al., 2024). This compound is a by-product of the manufacture and incineration of chlorinated substances; therefore, it could be non-intentionally released into the environment. Conversely, other residues such as PeCB, HCH, or

heptachlor showed contributions lower than 2 % in the majority of samples, and specific isomers including α -HCH, γ -HCH, or β -endosulfan were detected exclusively in shark meat.

The European Commission sets MRLs for pesticide residues in 315 fresh products intended for human consumption (European Commission, 2005, 2018). However, this regulation does not yet include fish,

fish products, or other marine food products, and therefore no regulatory frameworks apply to most of the samples analyzed in this study. The EFSA recently conducted a pesticide risk assessment on fish oil intended to act as a repellent on trees in forestry but, since this application does not contemplate human consumption, a consumer risk assessment was not deemed necessary (Alvarez et al., 2022). In contrast, MRLs are defined for sheep (including lamb and mutton) and berries. In both crowberries and blueberries, the MRL for most of the pesticide residues herein analyzed is 10 ng/g (with the exception of DDT and endosulfan, for which MRLs of 50 ng/g are defined). The MRLs for sheep commodities are in general higher, between 50 ng/g (endrin, chlordane) and 1000 ng/g (DDT). The OCP concentrations measured in the present study fell well below the established MRLs for all terrestrial matrices. However, the remarkably high levels detected in shark meat may raise concerns regarding potential dietary exposure despite the absence of specific MRLs. For instance, the DDT and chlordane concentrations in shark meat (11063 and 438 ng/g ww, respectively) exceeded the MRL set for sheep meat, another matrix of animal origin, by a factor of 10. A regulatory framework for pesticide residues in fish commodities is therefore essential to ensure consumer protection.

3.3. Legacy POPs: PBDEs and PBBs

PBDEs were identified at varying concentration levels depending on the type of matrix (Fig. 2c). The lowest PBDE loads were detected in meat, berries, and fish meat, with the only exception of shark (up to 97.47 ng/g ww). As previously discussed, the long lifespan of sharks and the bioaccumulation and biomagnification processes are the most likely causes of these findings. These compounds were also detected at markedly higher levels in fish liver and oil samples compared to fish meat in general (at least one order of magnitude lower), which reflects the preferential bioaccumulation of lipophilic POPs in fatty matrices over muscle tissues, as previously described (Julshamn et al., 2013; Karl et al., 2016). Conversely, when the summed PBDE levels are expressed in terms of lipid weight instead of wet weight –i.e., when the results are normalized according to the lipid percentage in the sample–, the differences among cod fillet, liver, and oil become less evident (*data not shown*).

Sample profiles of marine samples were dominated in all cases by BDE-47, while terrestrial samples showed in general a relevant contribution of BDE-209 (particularly in the case of berries), and puffin showed an intermediate profile with a low contribution of both BDE-209 and BDE-47 (Fig. 2d). These two congeners have been shown to have a widespread distribution in diverse ecosystems, despite the recent decrease of their levels in the environment (Giulivo et al., 2017; Li et al., 2023; Shunthirasingham et al., 2018). Additionally, highly brominated PBDEs such as BDE-209 have commonly been detected in plant samples by multiple studies, where atmospheric uptake has been identified as a dominant pathway (Dobslaw et al., 2021).

The three targeted PBB congeners (PBB-52, PBB-101 and PBB-153) were consistently detected in all marine-derived samples, although at substantially lower concentrations than most PBDEs (average concentration of 0.0024 ng/g ww in marine samples except for shark, compared to 0.0418 ng/g ww for PBDEs). In contrast, none of the PBB congeners were detected in lamb, mutton, or berry samples, while PBDEs were still measurable in these terrestrial matrices. This pattern suggests a stronger association of PBBs with marine food webs in the present dataset.

In 2021, Ho et al. analyzed eight PBDEs (namely BDE-28, -47, -99, -100, -153, -154, -183 and -209) in fish samples from the North East Atlantic Ocean, reporting concentrations in the same order of magnitude as those found in the present study for the same congeners (Ho et al., 2021). In their work, average levels in plaice and cod fillets were 0.09 and 0.02 ng/g ww, respectively, compared to 0.13 and 0.03 ng/g ww observed in this study. Although Ho et al. reported slightly higher concentrations in cod liver (6.07 ng/g ww compared to 1.79 ng/g ww observed in this study), the difference falls within the expected

variability given the geographical and temporal differences. However, the PBDE concentrations measured in shark muscle in the present study were markedly higher than those reported by Corsolini et al., in 2016 for the same species (Corsolini et al., 2016). In their study, BDE-47, -100, and -99 were found at 0.42, 0.00, and 0.01 ng/g ww, respectively, whereas in the present case, concentrations reached 55.56, 14.63, and 10.06 ng/g ww for the same congeners. A likely explanation for this discrepancy is the difference in age between the individuals analyzed: Corsolini et al. examined immature sharks, while the specimen analyzed here was an adult specimen, resulting in greater bioaccumulation. Geographic and temporal variations in the sampling of shark specimens may have also played a role in these different levels. The levels reported in the present study are also higher than those previously reported by Strid et al., in 2010 for Greenlandic sharks collected close to Iceland (Strid et al., 2010). As in the case of PFAS, no previous studies reporting the presence of PBDEs in terrestrial food samples from the Arctic could be found in the literature.

To date, no MRLs have been established by the European Commission for PBDES in food. However, a risk assessment recently published by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) concluded that dietary exposure to these substances raises health concerns due to potential developmental and reproductive effects (Schrenk et al., 2024). Specifically, the food commodity that is expected to contain the highest PBDE levels is, according to said study, fish liver. The same report included estimations of the Benchmark Dose Lower Limit (BMDL) for BDE-47, BDE-99, BDE-153, and BDE-209. Table 1 shows the concentrations of these four congeners in three representative matrices from this study, alongside the estimated daily intake (in kg of food per day) required to reach the respective BMDL values. Calculations were performed assuming a body weight of 70 kg and provide an indication of the minimum amount of food that could potentially result in adverse health effects, under the assumption of chronic consumption of unprocessed food. As can be seen, shark meat was the only commodity for which the estimated PBDE concentrations could represent a realistic risk of exposure: a daily intake of just 100 to 200 g would be sufficient to exceed the BMDL associated with neurodevelopmental and reproductive effects. These results highlight the importance of including shark meat in future monitoring and risk assessment studies, given the commercial availability of this item and its common consumption by Icelandic population during the midwinter festival of porrablót.

3.4. Legacy POPs: polychlorinated biphenyls, dioxins, and furans

The six non-dioxin-like (ndl) PCBs included in the analytical scope were detected in all samples, together with the majority of the 12 dioxin-

Table 1
Concentrations of selected PBDE congeners in three representative matrices, and estimated daily intake (kg of food for a 70 kg adult) required to reach the BMDLs associated with health effects (Schrenk et al., 2024).

Congener	BDE-47	BDE-99	BDE-153	BDE-209
Levels detected				
Wild Salmon (ng/g ww)	0.058	0.007	0.001	0.023
Shark Meat (ng/g ww)	55.564	10.059	2.420	0.054
Cod Liver (ng/g ww)	1.297	0.046	0.005	0.034
Neurodevelopmental effects				
BMDL (ng/kg bw · day)*	1096	3575	3.2	5000
Wild salmon amount (kg/day)	1313	34487	174.5	14933
Shark meat amount (kg/day)	1.4	24.9	0.1	6458
Cod liver amount (kg/day)	59.1	5427	44.3	10200
Reproductive effects				
BMDL (ng/kg bw · day)*	168	38.4	ND	3000
Wild salmon amount (kg/day)	201.3	370.4		8960
Shark meat amount (kg/day)	0.2	0.3		3874
Cod liver amount (kg/day)	9.1	58.3		6120

like (dl) PCBs. As can be seen in Fig. 2e, the number of PCB congeners did not vary significantly across most food items; however, as observed for other chemical families, there were substantial differences in the total PCB load of the samples depending on the type of matrix. The distribution of summed concentrations in the samples was similar to that of PBDEs and OCPs: shark levels (4997 ng/g ww) were several orders of magnitude above the remaining samples, followed by fish liver (up to 28.6 ng/g ww) and mackerel crude oil; cod fillet, cod liver oil, and plaice fillet showed comparatively lower levels, as did meat and berry matrices except for puffin (10.6 ng/g ww). The total PCDD/F load also mirrored this trend: shark displayed a total of 29.9 pg/g ww, while the next highest levels, in mackerel crude oil, were 5.6 pg/g ww (Fig. 2g). However, in this case, cod liver oil and berry samples showed lower contaminant diversity: less than 10 out of the 17 PCDD/Fs included in the analytical scope were detected.

All PCB sample profiles (Fig. 2f) were dominated by ndl congeners, which accounted for 79-92 % of the sample loads. These results are not surprising given that the ndl-PCBs included in the present study encompass six out of the seven indicator PCBs, which represent a significant proportion of the total PCB load in most ecosystems and are commonly used as benchmarks in environmental and biological samples (Liu et al., 2011; Van Leeuwen et al., 2007). All marine samples and puffin were generally dominated by PCB 153, which was also the dominant congener in previous studies on fish samples from the Arctic (Carlsson et al., 2014; Dale et al., 2019; Nøstbakken et al., 2015). Conversely, PCB 52 was generally the most abundant in lamb, mutton, and berries. Among the dl congeners, PCB 118 (the seventh indicator PCB) was the most abundant in all samples. The levels of this compound were comparable to or even higher than those of some ndl-PCBs, in contrast to other dl-PCBs, whose levels were usually several orders of magnitude lower. These distribution patterns have also been previously described in animal tissues from Arctic regions (Nøstbakken et al., 2021;

Sørensen et al., 2016).

Overall, the PCB concentrations found in the present study align with those previously reported in the same Arctic food matrices, given the variabilities expected due to different geographical origin of the samples and sampling years (Table 2). Farmed salmon from Iceland showed in this study comparable levels to Norwegian farmed salmon samples from multiple previous studies (I. J. Jensen et al., 2020; Lundebye et al., 2017; Nøstbakken et al., 2015, 2021), and the levels in wild salmon reported in the literature were also higher in all cases. Both dl- and ndl-PCBs accumulate preferentially in liver over muscle: up to 2230-fold differences have been reported between these two tissues in cod (Karl et al., 2016). This tissue-specific bioaccumulation likely explains the higher PCB levels recently reported in puffin by Abass et al., as these authors employed puffin liver samples rather than muscle (Abass et al., 2022).

Conversely to PCBs, significant differences could be observed for the PCDD/F profiles (Fig. 2h): furans were the dominant compounds in puffin and most marine samples, and dioxins accounted for more than 52 % in most terrestrial samples and certain fish species, a pattern previously reported in marine biota from the Arctic (Sørensen et al., 2016). 2,3,7,8-TCDF was typically the major contributor, in line with earlier works that reported this compound as the predominant homolog in marine organisms from Iceland (Falandysz, Smith, Steel, & Fernandes, 2019), the Baltic Sea (Falandysz, Smith, Panton, & Fernandes, 2019; Sørensen et al., 2016), or the Norwegian coast (Nøstbakken et al., 2021). The PCDD/F levels measured in the present study were generally lower than those reported in previous works for similar Arctic marine samples. For instance, Struciński et al. reported summed concentrations of 2.22, 0.21, and 6.74 pg WHO-TEQ/g ww in wild salmon, cod fillet, and cod liver, respectively, whereas the corresponding values in the present study were 0.06, 0.01, and 0.41 pg WHO-TEQ/g ww (Struciński et al., 2013). In 2010, elevated PCDD/F levels were reported in terrestrial food products such as beef, sheep meat, and milk in Northwest Iceland, as a

Table 2

PCB levels detected in the literature for Arctic samples.

dl-PCBs (77, 81, 126, 169, 105, 114, 118, 123, 156, 157, 167, 189), expressed in pg TEQ/g ww								
Wild Salmon	Farmed salmon	Cod fillet	Plaice fillet	Cod Liver	Puffin	Blueberries	Location	Ref
0.060	0.215	0.012	0.044	2.903	0.872	0.001	Iceland	This study
0.546		0.024	0.177	11.001			NE Atlantic Ocean	Ho2021
4.250		0.670		21.710			Baltic Sea	Strucinski2013
2.700		0.360					North Sea	VanLeeuwen2007
5.310		0.340					Baltic Sea	Piskorska-Pliszczynska2012
0.570	0.290						Norway	Lundebye2017
0.950	0.170						Norway	Jensen2020
	0.700						Norway	Nostbaken2015
	0.300						Norway	Nostbakken2021
		0.254		68.930			W Baltic Sea	Karl2016
		0.013		28.990			S Norway	Karl2016
		0.000		11.300			N Norway	Karl2016
		0.020		5.100			Barents Sea	Karl2016
		0.008		3.000			S Greenland	Karl2016
ndl-PCBs (28, 52, 101, 138, 153, 180), expressed in ng/g ww								
Wild Salmon	Farmed salmon	Cod fillet	Plaice fillet	Cod Liver	Puffin	Blueberries	Location	Ref
3.303	4.892	0.539	0.618	23.089	8.549	0.059	Iceland	This study
5.090	3.340						Norway	Jensen2020
6.600	4.000						Norway	Lundebye2017
6.315		0.540	1.587	101.190			NE Atlantic Ocean	Ho2021
36.200		1.110					Baltic Sea	Piskorska-Pliszczynska2012
0.793	6.660						Baltic Sea	Sorensen2016
		0.600		92.000			Norway	Nostbaken2015
			1.476				Barents Sea	Julshamn2013
				137.628			Norway	Kendler2023
					265 ^a		Norway	Dale2019
							Alaska	Ricca2008
						0.095	Finland	Abass2022
						0.129 ^b	Finland	Nalbandyan-Schwarz2024

^a Liver sample.

^b Mixed berries.

result of routine emissions from a waste incinerator operating in Skutulsfjörður (Halldorsson et al., 2012). Concentrations in these products exceeded 3 pg WHO-TEQ/g fat. By comparison, the levels detected in lamb and mutton in the present study (0.2 pg WHO-TEQ/g fat) were substantially lower, which is consistent with the geographic distance between the affected area and the present sampling locations. To our knowledge, no additional studies have reported PCB or PCDD/F levels in sheep from Iceland or other Arctic regions, limiting the possibilities for further comparison. Similarly, no previous data are available on the occurrence of these contaminants in Arctic berries.

The ndl-PCB set analyzed in the present study, also referred to as ICES-6, is contemplated under Commission Regulation (EU) 2023/915 on MRLs for certain contaminants in food commodities (European Commission, 2023). Similarly, the dl-PCBs and PCDD/Fs herein analyzed are also regulated under the same legislation, expressed as WHO toxic equivalents (TEQ). In all cases, these maximum levels are defined on an upper-bound basis –i.e., assuming that non-quantified congeners are present at their respective limits of quantification. As shown in Table 3, most of the concentrations measured in the present study were below the regulatory limits. However, the exceptionally high concentrations observed in shark and puffin raise potential concerns regarding dietary exposure to these compounds. Shark levels surpassed the corresponding MRLs in all three categories, with detected concentrations that were up to 35 times higher than their corresponding MRL (4418 ng/g ww compared to 125 ng/g ww for ndl-PCBs). In puffin, the levels detected exceeded the MRLs set for PCDD/Fs and for the sum of PCDD/Fs + dl-PCBs by a factor of 6.5 and 10, respectively. Although no specific MRLs have been established for ndl-PCBs in this matrix, the high levels detected (262 ng/g fat) exceed the limits set for other animal-derived foods. Lastly, no MRLs currently exist for dioxins, furans, or PCBs in berries or other plant-derived foods. However, the European Commission has established reference levels through Recommendation (EU) 2013/711, above which investigations should be carried out to identify and reduce the source of contamination (European Commission, 2013). For fruits, vegetables, and cereals, these levels are set at 0.3 pg/g TEQ ww for PCDD/Fs and 0.1 pg/g TEQ ww for dl-PCBs. The concentrations detected in crowberries and blueberries in the present study were well below these recommended values.

3.5. Simultaneous exposure to concurrent contaminant families

In terms of total concentration, organochlorine pesticides were usually the major contributor to the contaminant load of the studies set of samples (reaching up to 83 %) followed by PCBs (12-54 %). Fig. 3 shows the relative distribution of the four main contaminant families across representative food matrices, illustrating the co-occurrence of multiple pollutant classes within individual samples. PCDD/Fs were not included in this combined assessment due to their low contribution to the total contaminant load (<0.01 %). However, total concentration is not necessarily indicative of toxicological relevance, as the actual risk posed by a given contaminant depends on its specific toxicological potency. For instance, the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) defines a chronic reference dose (RfD) of 6×10^{-3} mg/kg-day for endosulfan, a representative OCP, while for 2,3,7,8-TCDD, a highly toxic dioxin, the RfD is as low as 7×10^{-10} mg/kg-day (seven orders of magnitude lower) (United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA US), 2025). Thus, despite the lower PCDD/F load compared to OCPs, the exposure risk posed by these congeners might be significantly higher depending on the specific levels present in the food products. This discrepancy highlights that total contaminant load at the family level cannot be directly interpreted in terms of health risk.

Furthermore, when multiple contaminants co-occur in a single food item, potential cocktail effects may arise, whereby combined exposure can modulate the toxicity of individual compounds (Huertas et al., 2025; Mantovani, 2016). The variable contaminant profiles observed across food samples complicates toxicological interpretation, as different contaminant mixtures may trigger additive, synergistic, or antagonistic effects depending on the specific compounds involved.

4. Conclusions and general remarks

The results of this study shed light on the presence and distribution of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in a selection of locally sourced Icelandic food items. Contaminant levels varied notably across matrices, with the highest concentrations detected in shark meat and marine oily matrices such as fish liver. These results confirm the biomagnification of lipophilic POPs in the food web, as well as their preferential bio-accumulation in fatty tissues. Shark meat, in particular, had the highest overall contamination, including PCBs and PCDD/Fs at levels up to 35 times higher than current European regulatory limits, and OCP levels

Table 3
Comparison of detected PCDD/Fs, dl-PCBs, and ndl-PCBs with EU MRLs.

Matrix	Table 3. Comparison of detected PCDD/Fs, dl-PCBs, and ndl-PCBs with EU MRLs						Unit basis
	PCDD/Fs (pg WHO-TEQ/g)		PCDD/Fs + dl-PCBs (pg WHO-TEQ/g)		ndl-PCBs (ng/g)		
	EU Reg.*	This study	EU Reg.*	This study	EU Reg.*	This study	
Wild Salmon	3.50	0.04	6.50	0.10	125.00	3.30	ww
Farmed Salmon	3.50	0.09	6.50	0.30	75.00	4.89	ww
Wild Char	3.50	0.06	6.50	0.25	125.00	11.94	ww
Farmed Char	3.50	0.11	6.50	0.35	75.00	3.03	ww
Cod Fillet	3.50	0.01	6.50	0.02	125.00	0.54	ww
Plaice Fillet	3.50	0.02	6.50	0.06	125.00	0.62	ww
Shark Meat	3.50	4.40	6.50	31.32	125.00	4418.31	ww
Cod Liver	-	0.41	20.00	3.32	200.00	23.09	ww
Hadock Liver	-	0.62	20.00	2.52	200.00	11.86	ww
Cod Liver Oil	1.75	0.09	6.00	0.11	200.00	0.65	g fat
Mackerel Crude Oil	1.75	1.06	6.00	3.36	200.00	18.82	g fat
Lamb Meat	2.50	0.20	4.00	0.32	40.00	9.85	g fat
Mutton Meat	2.50	0.23	4.00	0.38	40.00	9.64	g fat
Puffin	2.00	12.99	4.00	39.79	-	262.61	g fat
Crowberries	-	0.002	-	0.002	-	0.023	-
Blueberries	-	0.001	-	0.002	-	0.059	-

* Regulation (EU) 2023/915 (European Commission, 2023).

Fig. 3. Relative contribution of each contaminant family (OCPs, PCBs, PBDEs, and PFAS) to the total contaminant load (ng/g dw) in four representative food matrices.

exceeded those of the second most contaminated sample (cod liver) by almost 200 times. These findings support the need to establish specific regulatory limits for contaminants such as OCPs in shark meat, taking into account the consumption of this traditional food in Iceland. More broadly, the absence of MRLs for pesticide residues in fish and fish-derived products represents a regulatory gap that should be addressed to ensure adequate consumer protection. Conversely, PFAS levels in shark were lower than in other samples, suggesting that these contaminants may bioaccumulate and biomagnify through different mechanisms than lipophilic POPs. Among meat samples, puffin had the highest levels of all contaminant families, with similar profiles to those of fish. This is likely explained by its piscivorous diet, which increases its exposure to contaminants present in aquatic ecosystems.

In addition to concentration differences, distinct chemical profiles were sometimes observed between terrestrial and marine samples: PFOS accounted for more than 50 % of the total PFAS load in lamb and mutton meat, and BDE-209 dominated the PBDE profile in berries and mutton but was virtually absent in marine matrices. The lack of comparable data for non-marine foods in Iceland represents a major knowledge gap: most studies have traditionally focused on fish and seafood, neglecting other relevant dietary components.

It is important to emphasize that this study was conceived as a pilot screening exercise, with only one sample per matrix. The limited sample size restricts statistical comparisons, and the results should be interpreted as preliminary indications of contamination patterns rather than definitive exposure estimates. Nonetheless, this study provides preliminary data and identifies matrices of particular concern to guide future, large-scale monitoring programs and systematic risk management measures that reflect the complexity of dietary exposure to contaminants in Arctic environments.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

María Murcia-Morales: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation. **Karl Karlsson:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Conceptualization. **Kévin Barreau:** Validation, Investigation. **Anaïs Venisseau:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Thomas Le Bouill:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Frederic Larvor:** Methodology, Investigation. **Bruno Le Bizec:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Gaud Dervilly:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Gaud Dervilly reports financial support was provided by European Union. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known

competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2026.112134>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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